

New Scientific Opinion by the European Food Safety Authority: Bisphenol A in food contact material

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The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has published a new scientific assessment of the industrial chemical bisphenol A. In the following Opinion, the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) presents a synopsis of the content and reasoning behind the conclusions reached in EFSA's Scientific Opinion.

Through its assessment of experimental studies from 2007 to 2010, EFSA reached the conclusion that the latest data do not necessitate a change in the tolerable daily intake (TDI) for bisphenol A. The current TDI was determined by EFSA in 2007 and is set at 0.05 mg per kilogram body weight.

In its Scientific Opinion, EFSA notes that some of studies on the developmental toxicity of bisphenol A which were used for the assessment include data whose relevance for human health is undetermined. These are studies concerning the effects on the immune system, on biochemical changes in the central nervous system and the possibility of bisphenol A-induced enhancement of sensitivity in regard to breast cancer development. The Scientific Opinion shall again be reviewed as soon as additional data on these aspects that can be used for a risk assessment of bisphenol A become available.

In November 2010, the European Commission resolved to ban the sale and import of baby bottles that contain bisphenol A for reasons of preventive consumer protection. The precautionary principle addresses the uncertainties of the risk assessment.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/216/neues_gutachten_der_europaeischen_behoerde_fuer_lebensmittelsicherheit_bisphenol_a_in_lebensmittelkontaktmaterialien.pdf